

The Experience of a Romanian Veteran in International Missions: A Case Study on Psychosocial Resilience and Post-Military Reintegration

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Abstract

The present study analyzes, through an in-depth narrative interview, the professional career and subjective experience of a veteran of the Romanian Army who participated, within the International Security and Assistance Force (ISAF), in two international missions in Afghanistan (2008 and 2009-2010). The qualitative data resulting from the interview reveal three main analytical dimensions: (1) the formation of professional identity, as a result of distinct operational specializations (sniper and military cook); (2) coping mechanisms and psychosocial resilience developed in theaters of operations and (3) the transition process from military to civilian life and related reintegration after almost two decades of military career. The results underline the importance and role of group cohesion, intensive training, emphasizing institutional support in the management of combat stress, increasing the psychosocial resilience of the military, but also of the group, essentially providing relevant perspectives for military social assistance services.

Keywords: ISAF missions, military career, military social work, post-mission reintegration, psychosocial resilience, Romanian Army, Romanian veteran, theater of operations.

Introduction

By acceding to the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) in 2004, Romania accomplished one of the most vital steps for national security, with the „transatlantic relationship representing the strategic bond that confers coherence and consistency to NATO actions” (Ministry of Foreign Affairs [MAE], 2021). Consequently, Romania became an important and reliable ally within the North Atlantic Alliance, alongside the other 31 members.

Prior to joining NATO, Romania participated with troops in external Alliance missions or under the auspices of the UN:

- IFOR – Implementation Force (1995-1996) and SFOR – Stabilization Force (1996-2004), NATO-led operations in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Ene, C. 1997);
- KFOR in Kosovo (March 2000) (Ministry of National Defense [MApN], 2000);
- OEF (Operation Enduring Freedom) – the mission in Afghanistan, launched in June 2002, which recorded its first two casualties in 2003 (Comisarul, 2014);
- Operation Alba in Albania (1997) (United Nations, 1997), as well as UN Missions in Somalia (June 1993 – October 1994), Rwanda (August 1994 – March 1996), and Angola (1997-1999) (Ministry of Foreign Affairs [MAE], 2023).

„During the first ten years of membership in the North Atlantic Alliance, Romania participated in operations in the Western Balkans, Afghanistan, Iraq, and North Africa. In these missions, the Romanian Armed Forces maintained a presence materialized in a number of 40,000 rotated service members within these theaters” (Manciu, 2014).

The mission in Afghanistan (2002-2021) represented the largest and longest external deployment of the Romanian Army since World War II. „Throughout the 19 years of participation with military structures in this theater of operations, 27 Romanian soldiers lost their lives in combat actions, and over 200 were wounded” (Cozmei, 2021).

Following the conclusion of the mission in Afghanistan, the Romanian Army continued to be active in several external operations and missions under the auspices of NATO, the EU, the UN, and the OSCE, with a maximum strength of 5,000 service members according to the Force Employment Plan for the year 2026, approved by the CSAT (Crasnea, 2026).

The participation of Romanian service members in external missions and their exposure to operational risk factors generated systematic needs for social support, both for active military personnel and for veterans and their families. In this context, the recognition of psychological disorders associated with military service, including Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), was consolidated in Romanian legislation through Law No. 168/2020 (Parliament of

Romania, 2020). This legislative step represented an essential milestone in institutionalizing support for soldiers, veterans, and their families, grounding the development of military social work and specialized research, which are also reflected in the field's scientific literature, such as the Romanian Journal of Military Social Work, serving as a framework for analysis and consolidation of applied knowledge.

The present study contributes to the specialized literature by qualitatively examining the experience of a Romanian veteran who fulfilled distinct operational roles—sniper and military cook—within the same theater of operations.

Methodology

Research Architecture

The conducted study utilizes a qualitative case study approach, epistemologically grounded in Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) (Smith et al., 2009). Thus, Smith (2009, p.11) defines IPA as „a qualitative approach to research components dedicated to examining how people make sense of their major life experiences. [...] it is phenomenological in that it wishes to explore experience in its own terms.”

The primary method of data collection is the semi-structured narrative interview, which allows the participant to reconstruct the lived experience in their own terms, thereby facilitating access to the subjective meanings of the described events.

The research objectives are:

1. capturing motivational factors and the formation of professional identity;
2. analyzing coping strategies utilized under extreme stress conditions;
3. identifying psychosocial assistance needs during the post-mission reintegration process.

Participant and Operational Context

The interviewee—Corporal (Ret.) Slabu Iulian Virgil (S.I.V.)—is a former professional service member of the Romanian Army, enlisted in October 2002 and transferred to the reserve in 2022, following nearly 20 years of a military career. He participated in two international missions in Afghanistan:

- **Mission I (2008):** deployed at FOB Masoud, Zabul Province, as a sniper;
- **Mission II (2009-2010):** deployed successively at FOB Masoud, FOB Mescal, and FOB Lagman, as a military cook within the Logistics Company.

Note: FOB (Forward Operating Bases) represents an advanced military base utilized by coalition forces in Afghanistan. FOB Masoud in Zabul Province is situated in southern

Afghanistan, an area known for high insurgent activity; FOB Mescal is a forward base utilized for regional security through patrolling and counterinsurgency operations; FOB Lagman is a base located in eastern Afghanistan utilized in stabilization operations in a strategic zone due to its proximity to Kabul and insurgent routes.

Data Analysis

The analysis aimed to identify recurrent themes through inductive thematic coding, an exploratory approach to qualitative data where codes and themes are generated directly from the collected data, without the use or influence of pre-existing hypotheses or theoretical frameworks (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The interview text was segmented into meaning units, subsequently grouped into higher-order analytical categories, correlated with indicators of military social work and presented in the results section.

Results

Formation of Military Professional Identity

S.I.V. describes his choice of a military career through the lens of internalized institutional values: *“I chose a military career because I wanted to be part of an institution based on discipline, honor, and responsibility.”* This narrative confirms theoretical models of organizational socialization in military institutions, where exposure to norms, discipline, rituals, and collective experiences contributes to the formation of professional identity (Soeters et al., 2003).

Attaining the sniper specialization is described as a result of individual performance: *“Following the results obtained during training and firing sessions, I submitted a report to be selected for specific training for this specialization, and after the necessary evaluations, I was assigned as a sniper within Company 2, Platoon 3.”* This dynamic reflects the importance of merit and performance, characteristic values of military culture, as well as the role of individual agency in building a career trajectory.

An element of significant analytical relevance for social work is the transition to the role of military cook during the second mission, determined by *“the operational needs of the unit,”* illustrating the identity flexibility demanded of soldiers in modern militaries and the importance of logistical functions for the sustainability of operations: *“An army cannot function efficiently without logistical support. Nutrition directly influences the morale, physical capacity, and concentration levels of the soldiers.”*

Institutional Recognition and Professional Validation

Institutional recognition was the result of the veteran's participation in international missions, materialized through diplomas, distinctions, and professional commendations based on merit, courage, and professionalism: *"For participating in the two international missions, I was awarded the NATO medal and certificates of appreciation attesting to my contribution to the successful fulfillment of missions conducted under allied command."* These forms of recognition transcend the symbolic dimension of reward, representing a confirmation of his professional contribution and his belonging to the military community.

The International Mission as a Personal and Professional Development Experience

The analysis of the interview reveals that participation in the missions in Afghanistan represented not only an operational challenge but also a personal and professional development experience: *"Direct experience provides a completely different perspective compared to the one you have prior to departure"; "Through professionalism, respect, honesty, and the experiences lived together both during training and missions... the values and experiences acquired remained a part of my life."*

Exposure to an environment characterized by risk, responsibility, and uncertainty contributed to the development of skills such as self-control, adaptability, and decision-making capacity under stress: *"Patience, self-control, discipline, attention to detail, and the ability to make correct decisions under pressure. A sniper must be calm, balanced, and very well-trained professionally."*

These findings align with specialized literature showing that operational experiences can contribute to consolidating psychological resources, developing resilience, and fostering durable adaptive mechanisms (Bartone, 2006; Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004). Moreover, Habib et al. (2018), within a thematic analysis of post-traumatic growth (PTG) experiences, identified six themes among military personnel and veterans: appreciation for life, re-evaluating the sense of purpose, improving personal human traits, building bonds and connecting with others, integrating into society, pride in one's heritage, and a sense of value to society.

Psychosocial Resilience and Coping Mechanisms in Theaters of Operations

Several adaptive coping strategies are identified from the narrative analysis. Thus, the first mission (2008) represented the participant's first direct contact with the inherent risks in the theater of operations—combat mortality: *"we lost comrades and had wounded colleagues."* This traumatic exposure is processed retroactively through anchoring in professional values and group solidarity, essential factors in increasing cohesion and resilience: *"Through training, respecting procedures, and trusting colleagues. Repeated*

training before the mission created the necessary reflexes to act effectively even in difficult situations.”

Group Cohesion — A Central Protective Factor in the Military Environment

The results of research conducted by Griffith (2009) indicate that “soldiers’ experience with unit leadership support and cooperative relationships among peers solidifies their identification with the unit, reduces the likelihood that they will leave the military, and increases their perceptions of combat readiness.”

The presented narrative analysis validates this research and highlights the fact that mutual support, interpersonal trust, and identification with the unit functioned as mechanisms of psychosocial protection, contributing to the efficient adaptation of the interviewee: “*total trust in colleagues and the willingness to support each other regardless of the situation,*” also emphasizing the role of repetition in managing combat stress: “*Repeated training before the mission created the necessary reflexes to act effectively even in difficult situations.*”

Multidisciplinary Intervention: The Role of the Military Social Worker vs. Psychological Support

The participant benefited from institutional psychological support following his first mission: “upon returning to the tank unit, I participated in sessions held by the unit psychologist.”

However, for a correct analysis within the sphere of military social work, it is mandatory to delineate clinical competencies from social ones. It must also be pointed out that in the Romanian Armed Forces, the specialty of military social worker, as defined in Euro-Atlantic systems (such as the Military Social Work model in the US or the UK), does not exist. In the absence of a professional corps of military social workers within combat or logistical structures, the specific duties of social case management are often dispersed.

Transition and Post-Military Reintegration

The process of transferring to the reserve in 2022, after nearly two decades in military service, is described by the interviewee as an “important change,” emphasizing that “*the values and experiences acquired remained a part of my life,*” especially “*discipline, respect, responsibility, integrity, and perseverance.*” This identity continuity suggests a high level of adaptability and a functional appraisal of military experience during the transition process to civilian life.

The relational dimension formed over two decades in the military environment can generate a sense of emptiness, perhaps even a predominant one, reflected in the following statement: “[I miss] *Comradeship, team spirit, and the feeling that you are part of a structure united by a common purpose.*” This experience can be interpreted as a manifestation of losing the sense

of belonging and camaraderie specific to military culture, phenomena frequently reported by veterans during transition periods to civilian life (Sachdev & Dixit, 2024). The existence of this dimension highlights the need for community support networks for veterans.

Discussion

The presented data confirm and nuance several directions from specialized literature. Firstly, intensive training prior to deployment can serve as a psychological protective factor, reducing the impact of military operational stress and facilitating adaptive functioning under risk conditions. Such preparation contributes to increasing the resilience of service members, with significant effects at both individual and group levels (Bartone, 2006). Secondly, a high level of cohesion is associated with a greater capacity to adapt to operational stress and a reduced vulnerability to symptoms associated with Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (Siebold, 2007; Cohen and Wills, 1985; Brailey et al., 2007).

Regarding post-mission reintegration, the presented case highlights that the duration of military service and the deep internalization of military values can function both as valid resilience resources and as risk factors for adaptation to civilian life, particularly through the difficulty of replicating the level of cohesion experienced in the military environment.

Conclusions

The present study offers a valuable qualitative perspective on the experience of a Romanian veteran participating in international missions, with direct implications for military social work practice. The main conclusions address: (1) the essential role of training and group cohesion as factors of psychosocial resilience; (2) the importance of institutional psychological support post-mission; (3) the necessity of transition programs tailored to the cultural and identity specificities of veterans.

The results also highlight the relevance of military social work in identifying and managing the psychosocial needs of service members and veterans, as well as developing support mechanisms designed to facilitate family reintegration. In this regard, military social work can contribute to consolidating individual and family resilience, preventing social isolation, and supporting the process of adaptation to civilian life after the conclusion of a military career.

The limitations of the study reside in the monographic character of the case and the self-reported data, which may be subject to retrospective distortions. Future research could extend the analysis to larger cohorts of veterans and could integrate comparative perspectives

between different military specializations, thereby contributing to the development of knowledge and specific interventions within the field of military social work.